

Characterization of hybrid silicate materials based on ceramic glazes and waste London underground dust

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ABSTRACT

In “London Underground” stations, a high concentration of dust particles containing organic and inorganic matter of varying chemical composition. “London underground dust” is created from train wheels and brakes grinding against steel tracks and collected in filtration systems. The experiment will focus on using “London Underground Dust” to colour the ceramic facing tiles intended for re-use in newly built London Underground stations. The phase composition, particle size distribution surface area, morphology, and thermal behavior of collected dust were studied by XRD, XRF, SEM-EDS, BET, heating microscopy, STA-MS, UV–VIS spectroscopy. The substrate tiles for glazing experiments were prepared from local London clay. The mixtures of glazes and collected or milled dust were sprayed on the substrate tile’s surface, dried and finally fired at 1060 °C. The influence of used materials weight ratio and dust milling time were shown as crucial parameters to obtain optimal final glaze colour.

1. Introduction

The London Underground (LU) as the world’s oldest metro system, opened in 1863 [1]. LU has 272 stations, 11 lines (District, Hammer-smith & City, Circle, Metropolitan, Jubilee, Victoria, Central, Northern etc.), more than 400 km of track, and is the biggest consumer of electricity in London. 45 % of tracks are underground and provide daily around 2.8 million journeys and transport around 5 million people [2–4]. Many London underground stations are iconic due to the use of unique heritage face-tiling systems. Some the facing tiles are cast from moulds provided by H&E Smith (i.e., a tile manufacturer which refurbishes tiles for the London Underground) and was originally designed by Leslie Green, i.e. the architect stands behind many iconic London Underground stations in the early 20th century [5].

The metro system is one of the major transport modes in many metropolitan areas. This underground system brings several problems a)

mainly from air quality [2,6,7], and dust, which can be affected by mechanical wear, piston effects, no quality ventilation and air conditioning systems, etc. [8]. b) is a producer of harmful particles during the excavation of new tunnels and c) tunneling procedures extracted millions of tons containing rock, sand, stone, and clay [9].

Significant problems with air quality arise due to tunnel dust. Tunnel dust can be defined into 2 types: One called non-visible and contains micro to nano-sized solid particles and liquids in aerosol form; and the second one visible, i.e., “coarser rubbish” presented everywhere on the platform, and can be described as a heterogenous complex of wood, plastics, textiles, generally organic and inorganic particles. In addition to coarse, finer particles are generated from repeated grinding of steel tracks and train wheels. The chemical compositions consist of carbon, iron, manganese, titanium, chromium, barium, copper, strontium, antimony, or others can be found not only in steel but also in concrete pavements or rubber parts of the brake systems [10–12]. The authors in

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review [13] talks about “Tube dust” with similar composition. Jung et al. [14] identified four major particle types in subway platforms: the first one contains Fe between 29–87 wt %, the second one the soil-derived; the third one as carbonaceous and the last one contains nitrates and/or sulfate compounds. In another study [15,16] it was published that the content of Fe-oxides supposed to be between 47–67 % and other species were determined (i.e., 1–2 wt. % quartz, 18 wt% carbon, 14 wt %). The analysis of evaluated dusts showed that the 94–97 wt% with $D_{50} \geq 1 \mu\text{m}$ and 63 % with $D_{50} \leq 1 \mu\text{m}$ contained iron compounds with Fe^{2+} oxidation state [17]. For dyes, particle sizes can be distinguished into a system of fine-grained $<1 \mu\text{m}$, medium-grained $1\text{--}10 \mu\text{m}$, and coarse-grained $>10 \mu\text{m}$. The most used particle sizes for art dyes are varied from 30 to $40 \mu\text{m}$ [18].

In the UK it will be around $5,000,000 \text{ m}^3$, predominantly of London Clay [19,20]. The planned future target in the UK is to reduce the amount of excavated soil going to landfill to 75 % by 2040 and to zero by 2050 [21]. According to historical research, “London clays” were described as uniform and homogeneous, and found in the London Basin geological formation. Assemblage typically consists of smectite, illite, kaolinite and chlorite minerals [19,22]. Unweathered London clay is often present as stiff to very stiff with a deep cracked blue clay, whereas weather-exposed material is usually corroded due to the iron oxidation processes [23,24] (conversion of ferrous iron to ferric iron). The oxidation processes significantly affected the colour change from blue to brown hard and promoted the removal of pyrite [9].

The idea of London Underground Dust and Clay utilization for facing tile repairs or replacement matches heritage requirements and sustainability principles. We can distinguish 4 approaches how to work with damaged tiles: the first is patch repair, the second is patch repair in sections, the third one is the strip and replacement, and the last is over-tiling or preparing new tiles [25–27]. The waste utilization takes place in all ceramic tiles’ materials. In the general substrate tile body consists of clay, kaolin, quartz and feldspar. The ceramic industry is nowadays exposed to the term Critical Raw Materials (CRMs), which is a problem with global mineral resources, but the production of silicate-based inks, pigments, frits, glazes, dyes for ceramic decoration is mainly exposed to supply chain risk [28].

One way to help reduce dependence on primary resources is to increase waste material utilization, including that which has not been found. Many authors focus on the raw materials can be subsequently reused for ceramic process example vitrified sanitaryware waste (VSW) [29], fly ashes or blast furnace slag [30,31]. Glaze, in simplified terms, is the glassy coating on a tile surface. It is considered an important layer covering the ceramic body [32]. Generally, glazes can be produced by the application of a suspension of oxides on the surface of the ceramic body by dip coating, spraying, brushing, or fusion, followed by subsequent heat treatment. Most glazes are based on silica frits as the glassy phase, alkali oxides as the flux part and other oxides which enhance the stability and properties of the formed glassy phase [33]. Industrial production generates large amounts of the potential dyes as such dust from electric arc furnaces (EAFD) from steel plants [34] from metallurgy dust [35], ultramarine blue pigment from mixed of industrial zeolite waste (IZW) and agricultural corn straw (CS) [36] powder brown-red from waste toners [37], eggshell, calcium-rich wastes (CRW) [38], automotive industrial waste [39], waste from processing chrome ore [40,41] focuses on the use of “rock dust” for the preparation of ceramic glazes.

The use of inorganic dyes for ceramic glazes from a waste source such as the London Underground serves as an alternative to virgin mined materials in ceramic production. Additionally, this waste material can be saved from landfill as it is cleaned from tunnels and disposed of in landfills by Transport for London. The process of the train wheels grinding against tracks creates iron oxide particles small enough for ceramic production. The sustainability, design and ceramics may be connected. Study present the utilization of waste “London Underground Dust” and “London Clay”.

2. Materials and method

Fig. 1 summarizes the step-by-step process of preparing glazes from London Underground Dust (labelled as LUD) applied on raw London Clay (labelled as LC).

2.1. Materials

Initial samples were collected from various stations throughout the London Underground, mainly on the Northern, Central, Piccadilly, Bakerloo and Victoria lines with no significant difference in the quality of iron oxide. As the London Underground has heavy use year-round, there is no drop-in quantity of iron oxide produced at different times. Most of the iron oxide is accumulated over time and deposited as residue along the walls and floors of tunnels and tracks.

For experiment the “London underground dust” was collected from line the north-bound Bakerloo Line by quick method of vacuuming the platform of station Piccadilly and Oxford Circus (see in detail in Fig. 2). The tunnel on the Bakerloo Line is a deep-bored tunnel with embedded London clay at a depth of about 28 m below the surface and has an external radius of 1.953 m [1]. Collected dust is a heterogeneous mixture composed of plastics, wood, inorganic materials, stones, hairs, textiles etc. Before further processing, the primary LUD was sieved under the 0.063 mm mesh to eliminate large pieces in the mixture. This 0.063 mm upper size limit was based on experiences published by authors with similar powdered waste material [42].

Local London clay (labelled as LC) was taken from „Borehole“ [43] the Tideway super sewer project. Fig. 3A and B show the LC laboratory treatment for preparing tested ceramic specimens. The raw unfired clay is naturally darker to bluish in colour, which turns more orange after firing. Fig. 3A shows the raw unfired and unprocessed clay taken directly from a borehole sample. In Fig. 3B, this clay is crushed and dried before water is added for filtration and processing. In Fig. 3C, this clay is reconstituted with water, and Fig. 3D shows this clay after firing in a kiln. As a glaze matrix, commercially available powders were used (transparent and white glazes from production of Glazura s.r.o, Roudnice nad Labem, TORRECID GROUP, Czech Republic). The transparent glaze (labelled as TG) type from P series is a transparent, lead-free, colourless, shiny frit glaze without the content of lead oxide. Due to their high chemical resistance, glazes are especially suitable for utility ceramics and tile materials. This glaze is suitable for reducing the coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE) thereby eliminating or reducing unwanted cracking. They are intended for white and coloured burning shards with a coefficient of thermal expansion (CTE; $20\text{--}500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$; $52\text{--}70 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ K}^{-1}$), directly $47 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ K}^{-1}$. The white glaze (labelled as WG) from series Pw is a reliable lead-free white frit glaze. They have high coverage, good gloss, and considerable chemical resistance due to zirconium silicate presence. The white glaze has a low thermal expansion and therefore a small tendency to crack. It is suitable for white and coloured burning shards with CTE ($20\text{--}500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) of $55\text{--}75 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ K}^{-1}$, directly $58 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ K}^{-1}$.

2.2. Experimental procedure

As a glaze substrate, the ceramic tiles with dimensions of $(5 \times 5 \times 2, 1 \times w \times h)$ cm from original London clay were laboratory prepared. Chemical composition of used LC is given in Table 2. London clay was preliminary dried at $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 24 h, than crushed into 1 cm diameter pieces, mixed with water to prepare a slurry, and finally filtered to ensure its homogeneity. A gypsum form was used for easy shaping and assurance of size and quality of samples. After the unmolding, the tiles were dried at $105 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to constant weight and fired at $1060 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 5 h. After firing, the specimens color turned to reddish (Fig. 3C). Sometimes as a effect of varying oxidation states of Fe, 4–5 mm light brown/red surface layer with the black core from ferrous minerals was formed [44, 45]. For obtaining optimal consistency, each glaze mixture G0-G19 was

Fig. 1. Scheme of the experimental part of the article.

Fig. 2. A–platform Caledonian Road and process of vacuuming, B–original London underground dust (LUD), C–sieved LUD under mesh 1 mm and D–sieved LUD under 0.063 mm.

Fig. 3. A, B– original London clay after mining; C –London clay for experiment; D–London clay after fired at 1060 °C.

mixed for 10 min with a water in a laboratory alumina ball mill. Homogenous glaze slurry was than applied to the surface of ceramic tiles by spraying. This application was optimal for ensuring a compact layer of glaze on a ceramic surface relative to the same layer thickness and defect prediction. After the heating, the samples were allowed to cool down naturally in a furnace. The samples designated G0-G9 (series I.) were mixtures without any pre-treatment and samples designated G10-G19 (series II.) were glazes with pre-treatment, i.e. LUD milling with conditions given in Table 1.

2.3. Characterization methods

The chemical composition of ash was determined by a method of energy-dispersive X-Ray fluorescence spectroscopy (ED-XRF) on the SPECTRO XEPOS (Spectro Analytical Instruments, Kleve, Germany). The mineralogical composition (XRD) of samples was evaluated using X-Ray diffraction analysis on the X-Ray diffractometer MiniFlex 600 equipped 270 with Co tube and D/teX Ultra detector. The XRD patterns were recorded in 5–90° 2θ range with a scanning rate of 5° × min. (Rigaku, Japan). Measured XRD patterns were evaluated with Highscore program to obtain qualitative phase composition.

The granulometry – particle size distribution (PSD) of underground

Table 1
Proportional representation of individual components in the glaze [g].

Labels of samples	Materials		
	London Underground dust (LUD)	Transparent glaze (TG)	White glaze (WG)
G0	10	–	–
G1	5	–	5
G2	5	10	–
G3	10	20	–
G4	5	5	–
G5	5	–	20
G6	2	5	–
G7	2	–	5
G8	2	10	–
G9	5	–	20
G10	5 LUD–20	–	–
G11	5LUD–5	–	–
G12	5LUD–20	–	5
G13	5LUD–5	–	5
G14	5LUD–30	–	5
G15	5LUD–10	–	5
G16	4LUD–240	–	20
G17	4LUD–120	–	20
G18	5LUD–240	20	–
G19	10LUD–120	20	–

Note: sample “5-LUD20” ...5 g of underground dust, LUD ... London underground dust and 20 ... milling time in minutes of LUD in vibratory disc mill.

Table 2
Chemical composition of materials tested by XRF analysis.

Oxides (wt. %)	Materials (wt%)			
	London Underground Dust (LUD)	Transparent Glaze (TG)	White Glaze (WG)	London Clay (LC)
Na ₂ O	5.04	5.50	3.16	0.25
MgO	0.78	<0.3	0.27	2.35
Al ₂ O ₃	2.97	9.10	10.64	16.30
SiO ₂	47.70	82.10	53.05	59.50
P ₂ O ₅	0.30	<0.01	0.01	0.257
SO ₃	0.91	0.12	–	1.65
K ₂ O	0.98	0.88	2.54	3.76
CaO	7.41	0.30	8.63	1.29
TiO ₂	0.28	0.13	0.20	1.12
MnO	0.10	0.006	0.03	0.102
ZnO	–	–	3.67	–
ZrO ₂	–	–	15.58	–
Fe ₂ O ₃	10.5	0.22	–	7.81
BaO	–	0.05	–	0.05
Cl	6.70	–	–	–
Loss on ignition	15.96	1.4	1.4	5.37

dust was analyzed using equipment by Malvern Instrument by Aero method for range 0.1–1000 μm, (Malvern Panalytical Ltd., Malvern, UK). Colour measurement was performed by using Spectrophotometer (model MiniScan EZ0828, HunterLab, model 45°/0°, viewing area small) and measurement of the CIEL*a*b* coordinates CIE (Commission Internationale de l'Éclairage).

The instrument uses a xenon flash lamp to illuminate D65°/10°. The relative intensities of the light at different wavelengths along the visible spectrum (400–700 nm) was analyzed to produce numeric results indicative of the colour of the samples (HunterLab, Reston, Virginia, USA). The morphology of particles was analyzed by the scanning electron microscope SEM/EDAX QUANTA 450 FEG (FEI, Hillsboro, USA). BET specific surface area was measured using a sorption analyzer NOVAtouch LX2 (Quantachrome Instruments, USA). The sample was outgassed for 10 h at 50 °C under a high vacuum. A nitrogen-cooled (77 K) detector was used for the evaluation of the results using BET (Brunauer, Emmett and Teller) and Kelvin equations.

The Quantachrome software was used for the evaluation of measured data and to recalculate the measured value to m² per 1 g. STA-MS. The simultaneous thermal analysis combined with mass spectroscopy (STA-MS) was performed by the Setsys Evolution apparatus (Setaram, USA) up to 1000 °C. The measurements were performed in a dynamic air atmosphere with the flow rate 50 mL/min and heating rate 10 °C/min. The mass spectrometer (MS) OmniStar™ from Pfeiffer Vacuum (Germany) was used to analyse gases that evolved during heating.

Heating microscopy measurements were carried out using EM12 heating microscope (Hesse Instruments, Germany) on pressed 2.5 × 3 mm cylindrical powdered samples at a heating rate of 1 °C·min⁻¹ up to 1650 °C, with an image taken at least every 10 °C or when the shape or area of the sample silhouette changed. Obtained data was processed with Origin software.

3. Result and discussion

3.1. Chemical and phase composition of LUD and LC

The chemical composition of underground dust depends on various factors, such air quality, type and age of the underground station, tunnel design, the chemical composition of subway components (wheels, rail tracks, brake pads, and current supply materials), power system, train speed and frequency, passenger influx, ventilation and air conditioning systems, cleaning frequency, and other operational conditions [46–49].

Chemical analysis of the London underground dust, London clay, transparent and white glaze is given in Table 2. The Chemical composition of LUD exhibited a significant amount of silicon dioxide ~47 wt %, iron oxides ~10 wt%, followed by further components like aluminum oxide ~3 wt %, calcium oxide ~7 wt %, sodium oxide ~5 wt %, other alkali oxides are ~6 wt %. The observed amount of 7 wt % Cl may be problematic in further processing and final glaze quality. Oxides as Fe₂O₃, MnO, TiO₂, Cr₂O₃ should significantly influenced the colour of the fired product () and other ones as (MgO, K₂O, Na₂O) might act as fluxes and affected high-temperature processes [41].

London clay contained primarily silicon dioxide ~59 wt % and aluminum oxide ~16 wt % and iron oxides ~7 wt % and relative low quantity ~2 wt % MgO and ~1 wt % CaO. The contrast between the quantity of Al₂O₃ and CaO indicated the possible potential differences in the amount of presence of clay minerals and carbonates [19]. Generally, non-clay mineral are rich complexes of quartz, feldspar (albite and K-feldspar), carbonates (dolomite, siderite, and calcite), ‘mica’, pyrite, gypsum, and goethite. Clay mineral assemblages are generally formed of smectite, illite, kaolinite and chlorite [22].

The oxide content of SiO₂ a Al₂O₃ are controlled by changes of mainly minerals as quartz, feldspar, and phyllosilicate/clay minerals. The presence of CaO is a consequence of lower amounts of minerals such as limestone, traces of dolomite or gypsum. The amount of MgO reflected the presence of minerals such as smectite or chlorite. In transparent glaze, it was ~82 wt % and at white glaze around 53 wt%. The amount of ZrO₂ ~16 wt % was also determined in white glaze. All materials contained sodium oxide, potassium oxide, titanium oxide etc.

The powdered LUD had a relatively higher loss on ignition (LOI) values ~16 % than the value determined for LC (around 5 %). Both materials are heterogeneous and were taken from a real environment, also were not chemically adjusted. The critical variables for estimating the LOI were a) the weight of the tested sample, ignition temperature, burning time and particle size. According to the literature, the loss on ignition decreases with decreasing particle size (especially the size of particles in the range –1180 + 600 μm, –600 + 300 μm, –300 + 150 μm, –150 + 75 μm and –75 μm) [50,51]. This particle size influence was here also confirmed by BET and heating microscopy analyses (see Figs. 10 and 13).

XRPD patterns of LUD is presented on Fig. 4. We observed a presence of quartz in majority and other phases in minority - magnetite, halite, graphite (see Table 3). Phase composition is in good agreement with

Fig. 4. XRPD diffractograms of original London underground dust (LUD): 1 – quartz PDF No.01-078-1282, 2 – halite PDF No.01-080-399, 3 – graphite PDF No.00-056-0160, 4 – calcite PDF No. 01-080-9775, 5 – magnetite PDF No. 01-084-6696, 6 – albite PDF No. 01-089-6424.

Table 3

Quantification of particle size distribution measurements of LUD in dependence on the milling time.

London underground dust milling time (min)	Dv ₍₁₀₎ (μm)	Dv ₍₅₀₎ (μm)	Dv ₍₉₀₎ (μm)
0	5.03	25.5	66.6
5	2.37	24.6	101
10	1.55	11.9	67.1
20	1.24	7.13	44.0
30	1.15	6.42	35.5
120	0.70	3.79	21.6
240	2.51	27.3	13.6

data observed from XRF analysis. Determined phase composition of LC is given in Fig. 5. Quartz and kaolinite in majority, and muscovite, gypsum, vermiculite in minority were observed.

Fig. 5. XRD diffractograms of London clay (LC): 1 – quartz/PDF No.01-075-8322, 2 – kaolinite/PDF No. 00-058-2028, 3 – muscovite/PDF No.01-080-0742, 4 – vermiculite/PDF No. 01-076-0847, 5 – gypsum/PDF No. 01-076-8724.

3.2. Morphology of LUD

3.2.1. Original LUD

SEM images of LUD (Fig. 6) revealed a very heterogeneous structure with a high degree of agglomeration and various cluster particle size ranges. A variety of sizes, from nano to microparticles, was observed. The EDX analysis (Fig. 6B) confirmed chemical composition corresponding to the chemical composition observed from XRF listed in Table 2. In general, LUD particles were mainly in the form of agglomerates with spherical shapes. The micro-sized magnetite ones were spread out on the surface as larger agglomerates. The high average carbon content found in the iron oxide particles suggests that most of these particles may come from brake pads [68]. In a study [52], materials from the Munich underground were analyzed and showed similar overall shape and surface topography. They showed iron oxide particles found in all samples, predominantly with particles >2 μm in size. The iron oxide particles exhibited rough and often fragmented shapes with large surface areas due to the jagged edges often found in abrasion-derived particles. The shape and types of particles of powder relate to the degree of abrasion. The size of the particles released from an abrasion-free environment has been here defined as particles of approximately 200–500 μm (large), particles of approximately 30 μm (medium) and small particles of approximately 1 μm or less [53].

3.2.2. LUD pre-treatment: milling study

For further processing, we performed milling study to obtain optimal particle size for “colouring” of glazes. Particle size reduction depended on several factors as a type of milling, milling conditions, size of ball, used media shape etc. Vibrational milling has very pronounced mechanochemical effect and should produce fine particles in submicron sizes [54]. In first step the LUD was sieved by with 1 mm mesh sieve to eliminated larger species as sand, wood etc. Then the separated part was again sieved with 0.063 mm mesh sieve for subsequent milling. The sieved LUD was milled in laboratory vibrational disc mill (further labelled as VM) for 5, 10, 20, 30, 120 and 240 min. Mechanochemical effect is very pronounced. Samples were tagged according to the milling time as: LUD-0, LUD-5, LUD-10, LUD-20, LUD-30, LUD-120 and LUD-240. The original black dust as shown in Fig. 2D was changed by milling process to different shades of grey, see Fig. 7. From visual assessment with higher milling time, the powder LUD was lighter. Another way how to change the original colour of dye is a calcination at 900 °C and 1000 °C to investigate the colour effect of synthesized dye with different type of frits in industrial glazes [40].

The particle size distribution curves of milled LUD are shown in Fig. 8, and the results are summarized in Table 3. Milling effectivity was described by the values Dv₍₁₀₎, median particle size, Dv₍₅₀₎ and Dv₍₉₀₎ obtained for each single milling process (Fig. 8). The particle size represented by D50 gradually decreases with milling time from 5 to 120 min. We can also see the change in distribution from almost uniform to bimodal character with increasing milling time. Similar material was milled by Bernardin et al. [62]. Matte glaze for different times 15–50 min and they observed an average particle size ranging between 2.1 μm and 10.9 μm. A different situation occurred with milling time 240 min, particles started to agglomerate, and they had opposite progression than ones milled for lower time. This phenomenon was also previously observed for various materials such as [59]. Grinding system and particle reactivity should be a problem when particle size was reduced below 10 μm, interaction was occurring between particles [55]. Agglomerates can be formed due to the self-aggregating nature of powdered SiO₂ after only 10 min [69] the same results were published by Opoczky et al. [56], where the slow reduction in particle size of 90 h particles was associated with the formation of agglomerates. The published size of particles corresponded with them LUD milled for 5 min in VM.

The morphology of milled LUD is shown in Fig. 9. Observed particles (Fig. 9 A_{5min}) showed prismatic, flat, or elongated shapes and some

Fig. 6. The SEM images and EDX analysis of (LUD).

Fig. 7. The times of milling and colours of milled LUD.

Fig. 8. Particle size distribution analyses of un-treated and milled London underground dust (LUD).

irregularly round ones. The particles gradually became finer as the milling time increased from 5 to 240 min. The morphological shape of some particles seemed to be almost similar to Fig. 9 C_{20min}, D_{30min} and F_{240min}. All the SEM images showed the large-sized clusters/agglomerates of particles with the presence of smaller ones around 100 μm placed on the surface of larger ones. In the case of Fig. 9 samples F_{240min} after Table 3 the diameters DV₍₅₀₎ increased from 25.5 μm to 27.3 μm. Gülşen et al. published similar findings that gradual milling can induce a significant change in the particles' appearance due to the breakdown of the large particles into smaller irregular fragments [57].

The surface area of un-treated LUD was calculated as 7.98 m²/g. The obtained results are shown as inset of Fig. 10. BET Raw data can be found in Supporting information. If the material contains excessive amounts of cohesive fines, the density and permeability of the unbound

material will be relatively low.

3.3. Thermal behavior of LUD

The Thermal behavior of LUD was studied using STA-MS, where DTA and TG curve were recorded simultaneously together with MS signal for water and carbon dioxide (see Fig. 11 STA-MS). During heating, the sample lost 18.4 wt%. The highest weight decrease is connected to the oxidation of the organic part of dust, where the analyzer-wide exothermic effect starts at approx. 200 °C is obtained. Water was released/formed mostly between 200 and 400 °C, while carbon dioxide was detected up to 700 °C. The overall weight decrease was not extremely high, so we decided to use sieved LUD without calcination pre-treatment. Raw data for STA-MS can be found in Supporting

Fig. 9. SEM images from microscopy with parameter 100 μm and 50 μm of milled London underground dust (LUD). Milling times, A) 5 min, B) 10 min, C) 20 min, D) 30 min, E) 120 min and F) 240 min.

Fig. 10. BET Isotherms obtained by sorption analyzer for LUD.

information.

Figs. 11 and 12 show the thermal behavior of LUD before further processing. With increasing temperature, the LUD powder started to expand (from 200 to 900 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), which correlates with the exothermic phenomena connected to pyrolysis of organic part observed by STA analysis (see Fig. 11). Around 900 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ to 1200 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. the LUD started to

sinter with an area shrinkage of around 0.42 %. Sphere and hemisphere points were detected very close together in the range from 1350 to 1400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.

LUD started to melt at 1450 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ which correlated to the determined phase composition, i.e., combination of halite (melting point 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), magnetite (m.p. 1540 $^{\circ}\text{C}$), quartz (m.p. 1705 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) [58]. During thermal

Fig. 11. STA-MS Thermal analysis of LUD obtained by STA-MS.

Fig. 12. Heating microscope analysis of un-treated LUD.

treatment, the organic species started to decompose around 500 °C. Phenomena is related to area expansion (see Fig. 13A), similar temperature range of decomposition was also observed by STA-MS analysis (Fig. 11). All LUD samples started to sinter around 900 °C with different shrinkage rate. LUD with D50 below 0.063 mm, see Fig. 13A, had the highest area shrinkage than those above 0.063 mm and original LUD (see Figs. 12 and 13B). The higher values were related to the particle size distribution of the sample. Smaller particle sizes exhibited a higher sintering rate than the coarser ones. The data obtained are summarized in Table 4.

3.4. Thermal analysis of glaze mixtures

Commercial frits, white (WG) and transparent (TG), formed a uniform glaze between 1100 to 1360 °C and 1050–to 1260 °C respectively. The addition of different amounts of LUD significantly changed the behaviour. The organic species caused a significant expansion from 300 to 700 °C and strongly influenced the slope of the curves. The behavior was changed and was more irregular due to inhomogeneities in the sample, visible as bubbles or shape irregularities in the initial melt in Fig. 13B and 14B. In Table 5 the determined shape parameters are listed

and given in Supplementary data. In the case of the white glaze, significant expansion was observed from around 300 °C, with the expansion increasing as the LUD concentration increased. Sample G12 contained LUD milled for 20 min with D50 about 7 μm and behaved similarly to G1 and G5 (original LUD with D50 about 25.5 μm). Slightly different behavior in expansion was observed in the case of transparent glaze (see Fig. 14B). As the LUD concentration increased, the expansion was lower than for the white glazed samples (see Fig. 15). Sample G12 (containing LUD ground for 120 min with D50 about 4 μm instead of G3 and G4 with original LUD). Behaved significantly different. The smaller particle size resulted in higher shrinkage and also lower expansion, which is consistent with the data in Fig. 13A where the smaller particle size also resulted in a higher shrinkage rate. Similar behavior was observed by Pereira et al. [59], they studied ceramic colorants based on iron ore which also shifted the shape parameters towards higher values.

3.5. Characterization of final coloured glazes

The effect of the composition, firing temperature, milling technique and milling time of the glazes on the final colour is given in Tables 6 and 7. The colour as an object was here expressed in the CIE L*a*b* colour space. The coordinates L* represented the brightness of a sample; a positive L* value indicated a light colour/white colour/maximum is 100, while a negative one corresponded to a dark colour/black/minimum 0. Coordinates a* represented the green (–) and red (+) colour axis and b* the blue (–) and yellow (+) colour axis [73]. The L*a*b* values obtained for the studied glazes are listed in Fig. 6. The CIELab coordinates (L*, a*, b*) were further converted to the HEX code [60] way of representing colours. Table 6 presents the final colours of the prepared glazes with non-milled LUD. Series I. of glaze mixtures contain a combination of LUD + TG (samples G3, G4, G6, G7 and G8) or WG (G1, G2, G5, G9). The amount of the ingredients was always different. All glazes were fired at 1060 °C.

The surface of G0 has a matte appearance, others have a glossy surface. During the firing the original black colour of LUD changed to dark-red. The result was presented on the hue of the dye of sample G0, where final brick colour was almost identical to the substrate itself (fired London Clay). Dark aventurine tones to brown-black tones were observed in the case of glazes G1, G2, G3, G4 and G6. The tiles G3, HEX #3f290b [74], look very black with coordinates L* = 16.43 and a* = 2.91. The role of iron in glaze color was published in several works. Iron in silicate melt usually occurs in two valence states, Fe²⁺ and Fe³⁺. The Fe in the glaze was affected by the firing temperature, the atmosphere, and the acid-base property of the basis of a glaze [61,62]. High temperature, reduction atmosphere and high content of acidic oxides contributed to the reduction of Fe³⁺ whereas low temperature, oxidizing atmosphere and high content of alkaline oxides were favorable for the oxidation of Fe²⁺ [63]. This can result in a glaze with a higher Fe³⁺ content/brown-yellow colour and a glaze with a higher Fe²⁺ content/blue-green colour [61]. Only one G5 glaze was observed lighter compared to other samples. From visual an effect, it can be defined as light yellow with the coordinates L* = 63.88 and b* = 23.72 (yellow (+) colour axis). HEX code is #cca475 [74] composed of 80 % red, 64.3 % green and 45.9 % blue, a saturation of 46 % and a lightness of 62.9 % and colour description: slightly desaturated orange [64]. The glaze G7 was complicated for analysis, after were further converted to the HEX code is #977a5c [60] was composed of 59.2 % red, 47.8 % green and 36.1 % blue with a saturation of 24.3 % and a lightness of 47.6 % and colour description: mostly desaturated dark orange [64]. The glazes G8 and G9, #583e1f, can be called effect glazes due to small yellow dots formed on the glaze surface.

Table 7, series II. presents results from samples containing transparent and white glazes with milled LUD. At first glance, glazes G12, G13, G14, G15, G18 and G19 were brown-green to dark brown in colour. In contrast, glazes G10 and G11 were in red shades. In addition, these glazes were the only matt glazes. The lightest glazes were G16 and G17.

Fig. 13. Heating microscope analysis of milled LUD: A–D50 below 0.063 mm; BD50 above 0.063 mm.

Table 4
Heating microscope analysis data – calculated from shape and area curves.

Sample	Sintering (°C)	Softening	Sphere	Hemisphere	Flow	Area shrinkage (%)
TG	671	854	979	1056	1260	59
WG	651	884	1032	110	1362	77
LUD	892	428	1350	1396	1450	31
LUD <63 μm	896	480				53
LUD >63 μm	897	480	–	1450	n.a.	14

Note: „TG“... Transparent glaze, „WG“... White glaze, „LUD“... London underground dust.

Fig. 14. Heating microscopy analysis of white glaze mixtures: A–white glaze, B–white glaze with LUD.

The G10 glaze was ground for 20 min and applied separately on the ceramic shard. On the surface of the glazes from Fig. 7, a change of colour from dye to grey was also visible. However, after firing, the colour was brick red with small cracks on the surface. Only LUD without commercial glazes was used in samples G0, G10 and G11. All samples G0 (Table 6), G10 and G11 (Table 7) have a matt surface and dark/light/red colours very similar to the original LC.

Type G13 with LUD-5 min + WG is from visual assessment glaze was dark brownish-green. After specification of HEX #72634b [60] was composed of 44.7 % red, 38.8 % green and 29.4 % blue, a saturation of 20.6 % and a lightness of 37.1 %. Colour description: very dark grayish [64]. G14 was with LUD-30 min + WG. The resulting colour was observed a bland brown compared to the other colours. There was a visible round crack on the surface. Mixture G16 contained LUD-240 min

Table 5
Heating microscope analysis data for glaze mixtures – calculated from shape and area curves.

Sample		Sintering (°C)	Softening	Sphere	Hemisphere	Flow	Area shrinkage (%)
WG	G1	674	901	1063	1126	1258	73
	G12	675	912	1056	1181	1254	35
	G5	673	857	982	1045	1245	21
TG	G3	671	870	950	1011	1187	32
	G4	699	885	973	1031	1215	36
	G19	645	857	1047	1129	1322	66

Fig. 15. Heating microscopy analysis of transparent glaze mixtures: A–transparent glaze, B– transparent glaze with LUD.

Table 6
Colour analyses of glazes with non-milled LUD and coordinates of CIELab.

FINAL COLOURS OF GLAZES FROM LONDON UNDERGROUND DUST I.				
G0 L* = 42.62 a* = 11.98 b* = 10.79	G1 L* = 17.59 a* = 6.91 b* = 4.66	G2 L* = 16.07 a* = 5.11 b* = 9.13	G3 L* = 16.43 a* = 2.91 b* = 9.01	G4 L* = 30.77 a* = 4.32 b* = 4.86
G5 L* = 63.88 a* = 4.01 b* = 23.72	G6 L* = 19.69 a* = 5.18 b* = 10.73	G7 L* = 46.14 a* = 3.08 b* = 15.47	G8 L* = 28.36 a* = 7.33 b* = 23.10	G9 L* = 22.63 a* = 4.89 b* = 18.9

+20WG and HEX #ded9cf [60] was composed of 87.1 % red, 85.1 % green and 81.2 % blue, a saturation of 18.5 % and a lightness of 84.1 %, light greyish orange [64]. Samples G17 contained LUD-120 min +20TG HEX #d4c9ba [60] was composed of 83.1 % red, 78.8 % green and 72.9 % blue, a saturation of 23.2 % and a lightness of 78 %. Colour description: greyish orange [64]. Small black dots were visible in both light glazes. In the case of the longest milling time (240 min), the glaze

exhibited a lighter tone compared to the 120 min of LUD milling.

G18 with LUD-240 exhibited a slight dye overlay. The red shard shone through it. The G19 with LUD-120 had a visible pitting on the surface.

The final glazes can be assessed as compatible with ceramic surfaces from 80 %. In this experiment, pinhole, crack, and leaching were identified. Glaze G1, series I. has two hues of dark red and light red. This

Table 7

Colour analyses of glazes with milled LUD and coordinates of CIELab.

FINALL COLOURS OF GLAZES FROM LONDON UNDERGROUND DUST II.				
G10 L* = 42.96 a* = 12.06 b* = 13.52	G11 L* = 47.48 a* = 13.74 b* = 14.93	G12 L* = 39.55 a* = 1.14 b* = 9.44	G13 L* = 42.73 a* = 1.83 b* = 15.92	G14 L* = 34.75 a* = 5.50 b* = 7.74
G15 L* = 45.01 a* = 5.28 b* = 9.94	G16 L* = 86.93 a* = 0.01 b* = 5.60	G17 L* = 81.59 a* = 1.07 b* = 9.22	G18 L* = 40.03 a* = 4.46 b* = 5.60	G19 L* = 47.42 a* = 2.73 b* = 8.48

difference can be caused by poor application of the applied layer thickness. The small cracks were observed at glaze G10 only with LUD-20 min milled without added of other glazes. This problem occurred during the cooling part. This happens generally as the glazes cooled after firing. It is upon the cooling of the kiln and the various contraction of the glazes and tile substrates that led to crack formation. Heating and then cooling too rapidly can cause the glaze to shrink too quickly and cracks appear more readily.

The crazed glaze can be utilized as a decorative crackle effect. The solution may be the addition of low-expansion materials such as talc to LUD. A non-compatible relief on the glaze G3, G12, G14 and G18 were observed (i.e., pores and blisters). From a chemical point of view, materials such as calcium and barium carbonates, porcelain clay, talc, zirconium silicate and organic compounds are subjected to gas evolution during the decomposition of these materials during firing. LUD can exhibit similar behavior due to its phase composition (i.e. calcite and halite presence). In addition, quartz also serves to increase the retention of these gases e.g. Ref. [65]. Several factors were involved in the formation of holes, such as CO₂/CO and sometimes SO₂/SO₃, which were formed by the decomposition of some salts in the glaze mixture, such as carbonates.

Small bubbles have virtually no effect on the quality of the glaze and can be neglected, especially if they were isolated from the outer surface of the glaze. However, if the bubbles become larger or closer to the surface, they can distort the surface and cause a mismatch. This can be caused by under firing or overfiring the glaze, bubbles haven't time to heal over due to gas release. A possible solution was to hold the firing at top temperature for a longer period to allow bubbles to settle. The evaporation of water also created small pores between the glaze grains. The pores were minimal if the glaze grains were fine [66]. The bubbles are most likely due to human application errors or the glaze was applied too thick on the clay. The second problem observed was the spraying technique, during the coating the bubbles can be formed due to an excessive number of layers. Bubbles should also certainly appear if the first layer dried too quickly. When the first layer contains some surface porosity, the trapped air can escape and form consequent pores and bubbles in further layers. During application, it was necessary to ensure the wetting of the first layer [65,67]. Adjusting the grain size of the glaze affected its surface properties. Most studies concluded that reducing the glaze grain size leads to a reduction in glaze viscosity, which ensures easy escape of gas bubbles. On the other hand, if the glaze particle size is

excessively reduced, the air absorption by the glaze will increase during the spraying process and can cause porosity in the glaze layer [68,69].

4. Conclusion

European strategies for Green Deal and Safe and Sustainable by Design foster all actions to climate neutrality, circularity, zero pollution, transparency trackability and a toxic-free environment. Ceramic tiles are a defining feature of the London Underground, the world's oldest metro system, yet their material origins are often unknown. Typically, virgin resources extracted through open-pit mining are used in production. To address this issue, these tiles are made from the waste produced during the construction and operation of the London Underground itself. The next materials forming in London Underground is dust contain iron oxide-rich dust from train wheels grinding against steel tracks. The use of London dust is realistic as a dye for the preparation of glazes with the corresponding colour typical for London Underground. However, according to the obtained results the mechanical pre-treatment is necessary due to the very heterogenous original LUD form. Glazes applied to London Clay ceramic substrates exhibited good adhesion without any layer separation or cluster crystallization. The final glaze colour was significantly affected by milling time of original LUD. It has found the optimal process how to produce glazed tiles that can be a full replacement for the existing tiles that belong to the architectural heritage of Great Britain.

Data statement

According to Open Science principles, raw data can be found at. DOI raw data 10.5281/zenodo.11472380.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Hana Ovčáčková: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology. **Jeffrey Stephen Miller:** Investigation. **Vlastimil Matějka:** Visualization, Supervision, Formal analysis. **Eva Bartoníčková:** Writing – review & editing, Formal analysis, Data curation. **Ondřej Jankovský:** Writing – review & editing, Data curation. **Jozef Vlček:** Project administration, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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